

Vasil Cvetkov

Chief Assist. Prof. PhD Eng.

University of Architecture, Civil Engineering and Geodesy.

1164, 1 Hristo Smirnenski Blvd. Sofia, Bulgaria

ORCID: 0000-0001-9628-6768

Abstract

The current manuscript discusses the relationship between the standard deviation σ of samples of size n random numbers and the standard deviation σ_{MTE} of the synthetic sample of these observations from origin samples, which have the least true errors. In addition, the relationship between the standard deviation σ of samples of size n random numbers and the standard deviation σ_{MTEA} of the combined synthetic sample of the observations with the least true errors and those averages near the true value of the quantity than observations is also analyzed. The research is based on simulations of random numbers from Normal and Uniform distributions with preliminary known parameters. Functional relationships between standard deviations σ_{MTE} and σ_{MTEA} , the sample standard deviation σ , the entropy of the standard normal distribution $N(0, 1)$, and the sample size n , where $n=\{1, 2, 3, \dots, 100\}$, were found. It is also shown that the inequality $\sigma_{MTEA} < \sigma_{MTE} < \sigma_{\bar{X}}$, where $\sigma_{\bar{X}}$ is the standard deviation of the mean of $n > 1$ observations, is valid. Moreover, the ratios $\sigma_{\bar{X}} / \sigma_{MTE}$ and $\sigma_{\bar{X}} / \sigma_{MTEA}$ get bigger when $n \rightarrow 100$. For example, if $n=3$ the $\sigma_{\bar{X}} / \sigma_{MTEA} > 1.75$, if $n=10$ $\sigma_{\bar{X}} / \sigma_{MTEA} > 2.6$, and if $n=100$ $\sigma_{\bar{X}} / \sigma_{MTEA} > 6.4$ in the case of Normal distribution. In the case of Uniform distribution, if $n=3$ the $\sigma_{\bar{X}} / \sigma_{MTEA} > 1.45$, if $n=10$ $\sigma_{\bar{X}} / \sigma_{MTEA} > 2.15$, and if $n=100$ $\sigma_{\bar{X}} / \sigma_{MTEA} > 4.6$. In addition, increasing the sample size n leads to the convergence of σ_{MTE} to σ_{MTEA} . The above conclusions are valid for both Normal and Uniform distributed data, which implies that they will be valid for any arbitrary continuous distribution data with finite variance. Considering the simulation results, modern data analysis should be based on the observations with the least true errors rather than only the arithmetic mean.

Keywords: Arithmetic Mean, Entropy, Normal Distribution, Sample Size, Standard Deviation, True Errors, Uniform Distribution

Introduction

Suppose we have a sample of size n observations, namely $X_1, X_2, \dots, X_i, \dots, X_n$. Let σ be the standard deviation of our sample. Then, the standard deviation of each observation X_k will be σ because of equation (1).

$$\text{Var}(X_1) = \text{Var}(X_2) = \dots = \text{Var}(X_i) = \dots = \text{Var}(X_n) = \sigma^2 \quad (1)$$

Let \bar{X} be the average of observations $X_1, X_2, \dots, X_i, \dots, X_n$. Then, the standard deviation $\sigma_{\bar{X}}$ of the average \bar{X} can be given by (3) because of (2) [3, among others].

$$\text{Var}(\bar{X}) = \frac{1}{n^2} \text{Var}(X_1 + X_2 + \dots + X_n) = \frac{1}{n^2} n \cdot \text{Var}(X_k) = \frac{\sigma^2}{n} \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_{\bar{X}} = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}} \quad (3)$$

That is to say, the standard deviation $\sigma_{\bar{X}}$ of the average \bar{X} is \sqrt{n} times fewer than the standard deviation of any arbitrary observation in the sample $X_1, X_2, \dots, X_i, \dots, X_n$.

However, the probability that our sample contains an observation, says X_i , which has a less true error than \bar{X} is greater than 60% if $n=2$ and tends to 100% when $n \rightarrow \infty$ [2].

Let the standard deviation σ_{MTE} be the standard deviation of a sample formed by those observations X_m with the least true errors in m samples from a concrete distribution with known standard deviation σ . Let the standard deviation σ_{MTEA} be the standard deviation of a sample formed by those observations X_m and the averages \bar{X}_m with the least true errors in m samples from a

concrete distribution with known standard deviation σ . So, the main objective of the current research is to show that the ratios σ_{MTEA}/σ and σ_{MTE}/σ follow the law (4), which is a function of the entropy of the standard normal distribution $N(0, 1)$ [5] and the sample size n .

$$(\sigma_{MTEA} \text{ or } \sigma_{MTE})/\sigma = a \cdot n^{-b} - c \cdot n^{-d} \quad (4)$$

The secondary aim is to show that the relationship $\sigma_{MTEA} < \sigma_{MTE} < \sigma_{\bar{X}}$, where $\sigma_{\bar{X}}$ is the standard deviation of the mean of $n > 1$ observations, is valid.

In the current stage, we will constrain our investigation to Normal and Uniform distributed data and sample sizes up to 100 observations.

Simulations

We performed the below experiment to estimate the ratio σ_{MTEA}/σ for different distributions with different parameters.

1. We generated matrix $M(50000, 100)$ that contains 5000000 random numbers from an arbitrary distribution with arbitrary parameters. So, our initial matrix M has the form (5).

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} x_{1,1} & \dots & x_{1,100} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_{50000,1} & \dots & x_{50000,1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

2. Using the numbers in matrix M , we generated matrix $MEANS$ with means from the first to j -th member for each row i , as shown below.

$$MEAN = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{k=1} x_{1,j}}{k} & \dots & \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{k=100} x_{1,j}}{k} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{k=1} x_{50000,j}}{k} & \dots & \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{k=100} x_{50000,j}}{k} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

3. As the next step, we prepared the matrix *MTE*, which contains the observations with the least true errors in samples generated by the observations from the first to the *j*-th one for each row *i*.

$$MTE = \begin{bmatrix} X_{i=\{1,1\}}^{MTE} & \dots & X_{i=\{1,100\}}^{MTE} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ X_{i=\{50000,1\}}^{MTE} & \dots & X_{i=\{50000,100\}}^{MTE} \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

4. By comparing the corresponding members of the *MEAN* and *MTE* matrices, we generated matrix *MTEA* (50000, 100), which counts the minimum value between *MEAN*_{*i,j*} and *MTE*_{*i,j*}.

$$MTEA = \begin{bmatrix} \min(MEAN_{1,1}; MTE_{1,1}) & \dots & \min(MEAN_{1,100}; MTE_{1,100}) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \min(MEAN_{50000,1}; MTE_{50000,1}) & \dots & \min(MEAN_{50000,100}; MTE_{50000,100}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

5. Finally, we can create a σ_{MTEA}/σ matrix (9), which contains the standard deviations of the samples formed by the members in each column in the *MTEA* matrix divided by the standard deviation σ of the parent distribution.

$$\sigma_{MTEA}/\sigma = [\sigma_{n=1}^{MTEA}/\sigma \quad \dots \quad \sigma_{n=100}^{MTEA}/\sigma] \quad (9)$$

6. Performing steps 1 and 3 only, we can obtain the matrix σ_{MTE}/σ with the standard deviations of samples of the observations with the least true errors for the synthetic samples of size $n=1, 2, \dots, 100$.

7. We performed the above procedure, steps 1-6, for Normal distributions $N(0, 1)$, $N(0, 0.25)$, and $N(0, 9)$ and Uniform distributions $U(-1, 1)$, $U(-2, 2)$, and $U(-10, 10)$.

Results

Tables 1-4 give the relationship between standard deviations σ_{MTE} , σ_{MTEA} , and σ , the sample size *n*, and the entropy of the standard normal distribution in the cases of Normal and Uniform data. Figures 1 and 2 illustrate the relationship between the empiric and the synthetic values of ratio σ_{MTE} / σ regarding Normal and Uniform distributed data, respectively. Figures 3 and 4 show the relationship between the empiric and the synthetic values of ratio σ_{MTEA} / σ regarding Normal and Uniform distributed data. Figure 5 presents all results together.

Table 1

Coefficients a, b, c, d in equation (4) for the standard deviations σ_{MTE} for normally distributed observations.

Distribution	Coefficients	Range		
		n = 1	n = {2, 3}	4 ≤ n ≤ 100
Normal	a	$\frac{1}{2} * \log_{\sqrt{2\pi e}}(2\pi e)$	$\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4} * \log_{\sqrt{2\pi}}(2\pi e)$	
	b	$\frac{1}{2} * \log_{(\frac{3}{2}+\pi)}(2\pi e)$		
	c	0	$\frac{1}{8} * \log_3(2\pi e)$	0
	d	$\sqrt{2\pi}$		

Table 2

Coefficients a, b, c, d in equation (4) for the standard deviations σ_{MTEA} for normally distributed observations.

Distribution	Coefficients	Range		
		n = 1	2 ≤ n ≤ 5	6 ≤ n ≤ 100
Normal	a	$\frac{1}{2} * \log_{\sqrt{2\pi e}}(2\pi e)$	$\frac{1}{2} * \log_{(\frac{3}{2}+\pi)}(2\pi e)$	
	b	$\frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2}$		
	c	0	$\frac{1}{20} * \log_{\sqrt{2\pi e}}(2\pi e)$	0
	d	$\sqrt{2}$		

Table 3

Coefficients a, b, c, d in equation (4) for the standard deviations σ_{MTE} for uniformly distributed observations.

Distribution	Coefficients	Range		
		n = 1	n = 2, 3, 4	5 ≤ n ≤ 100
Uniform	a	$\frac{1}{2} * \log_{\sqrt{2\pi e}}(2\pi e)$	$1 + \frac{1}{4} * \log_{\pi}(2\pi e)$	
	b	$\frac{1}{2} * \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}}\right)$		
	c	0	$\frac{1}{4} * \log_f(2\pi e)$	0
	d	$\sqrt{2\pi}$		

*If n = 2, then f = π-1 ≈ 2.1416. If n = 3, then f = √2π ≈ 2.5066. If n = 4, then f = e ≈ 2.7183.

Table 4

Coefficients a, b, c, d in equation (4) for the standard deviations σ_{MTEA} for uniformly distributed observations.

Distribution	Coefficients	Range	
		1 ≤ n ≤ 5	6 ≤ n ≤ 100
Uniform	a	$\frac{1}{2} * \log_{\sqrt{2\pi e}}(2\pi e)$	$\frac{1}{4} * \log_2(2\pi e)$
	b	$\frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{4} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}}$	

Normally distributed observations

Figure 1: Relationship between the standard deviation σ_{MTE} of the sample created by the observations with the least true errors, standard deviation σ of the parent Normal distribution, and the sample size n, based on 150000 normal random numbers for $1 \leq n \leq 100$.

The coefficient of determination between the empiric and the synthetic ratio σ_{MTE} / σ , given in Figure 1, is estimated to be $R^2 = 0.9997$.

Uniformly distributed observations

Figure 2: Relationship between the standard deviation σ_{MTE} of the sample created by the observations with the least true errors, standard deviation σ of the parent Uniform distribution, and the sample size n , based on 150000 uniform random numbers for $1 \leq n \leq 100$.

The coefficient of determination between the empiric and the synthetic ratio σ_{MTE} / σ , given in Figure 2, is estimated to be $R^2 = 0.9996$.

Normally distributed observations + Means

Figure 3: Relationship between the standard deviation σ_{MTEA} of the sample created by the observations and means with the least true errors, standard deviation σ of the parent Normal distribution, and the sample size n , based on 150000 normal and 150000 uniform random numbers for $1 \leq n \leq 100$.

Uniformly distributed observations + means

Figure 4: Relationship between the standard deviation σ_{MTEA} of the sample created by the observations and means with the least true errors, standard deviation σ of the parent Uniform distribution, and the sample size n , based on 150000 normal and 150000 uniform random numbers for $1 \leq n \leq 100$.

The coefficient of determination between the empiric and the synthetic ratio σ_{MTEA} / σ , given in Figure 3 and Figure 4, is estimated to be $R^2 = 0.9999$ and $R^2 = 0.9990$ for the Normal and Uniform data.

Figure 5: Aggregate chart of the standard deviation ratios σ_{MTE}/σ , σ_{MTEA}/σ of the samples created by the observations and averages with the least true errors, standard deviation σ of the parent Normal or/and Uniform distribution, and the sample size n , based on 150000 Normal and 150000 Uniform random numbers for $1 \leq n \leq 100$.

Discussion

Analyzing coefficients a and c of equation (4) given in Tables 1-4, one can see that they can be presented in a general form (10), where $H_b [N(0, 1)]$ denotes the entropy of the standard normal distribution $N(0, 1)$ [4, 5].

$$(a \text{ or } c) = A + B \cdot \left[\frac{1}{2} \cdot \log_b(2\pi e) \right] = A + B \cdot H_b [N(0, 1)] \quad (10)$$

Using the logarithm property (11), we can rewrite the standard normal distribution $N(0, 1)$ entropy as a logarithm of $2\pi e$ with any arbitrary base a .

$$\log_b(X) = \log_a(X) / \log_a(b) \quad (11)$$

According to Tables 1-4, the base b depends on the data distribution and the sample size n . However, the base b of $H_b [N(0, 1)]$ and the coefficients a and c of equation (4) are invariant of the standard deviation σ of the data sample, derived from any specific distribution. As a result, the ratios σ_{MTEA}/σ and σ_{MTE}/σ are functions of the sample size n and changes in the entropy $H_b [N(0, 1)]$ concerning the increase of n . This fact has its natural explanation. When the sample size n is too small, say $n < 5$, the graphs of the ratios σ_{MTEA}/σ and σ_{MTE}/σ drop rapidly down. On the other hand, if the sample size is $n \geq 25$, the graphs of the ratios σ_{MTEA}/σ and σ_{MTE}/σ can be approximated by a straight line. When $5 < n < 25$ there are elbows in the graphs. The greater the distribution entropy, the greater the length of the elbow. This fact is clearly illustrated in Figure 5 by the graphs of the ratios σ_{MTEA}/σ and σ_{MTE}/σ in the case of data from Normal and Uniform distribution.

Similar behavior has the ratio $\sigma_{\bar{x}} / \sigma$. Based on (3), we can write (12).

$$\sigma_{\bar{x}} / \sigma = 1 \cdot n^{-0.5} = 0.5 \cdot \log_{\sqrt{2\pi e}}(2\pi e) \cdot n^{-0.5} \quad (12)$$

Thus, the standard deviation of the sample mean is also a function of the entropy of the standard normal distribution $N(0, 1)$ $H_b [N(0, 1)]$, the data standard deviation σ , and the sample size n . If we divide equation (12) by σ_{MTEA}/σ of the uniformly distributed data of size $n \geq 6$, we will obtain a ratio (13).

$$\sigma_{\bar{x}} / \sigma_{MTEA} = [1 \cdot n^{-0.5}] / [1.0235 \cdot n^{-0.842}] \approx 0.977 \cdot n^{-0.5+0.842} \approx n^{0.342} \approx \sqrt[3]{n} \quad (13)$$

Consequently, if $n=3$ the $\sigma_{\bar{x}} / \sigma_{MTEA} > 1.4$, if $n=10$ $\sigma_{\bar{x}} / \sigma_{MTEA} > 2.1$, and if $n=100$ $\sigma_{\bar{x}} / \sigma_{MTEA} > 4.6$ in the case of uniformly distributed data. In the case of normally distributed data, we calculated that if $n=3$ the $\sigma_{\bar{x}} / \sigma_{MTEA} > 1.75$, if $n=10$ $\sigma_{\bar{x}} / \sigma_{MTEA} > 2.6$, and if $n=100$ $\sigma_{\bar{x}} / \sigma_{MTEA} > 6.4$. Figure 5 perfectly illustrates the ratios σ_{MTEA}/σ and σ_{MTE}/σ in the case of both the normally and uniformly distributed data. Similar conclusions can easily be obtained for the ratio $\sigma_{\bar{x}} / \sigma_{MTE}$. Therefore, the sample means from any arbitrary distribution have greater standard deviations than the sample of observations with the least true errors.

Conclusions

This paper illustrated the relationship between the entropy of the standard normal distribution $N(0, 1)$, the sample size n , and the distributions of the observations in the sample (and) the sample mean. It was shown, that

the standard deviation of the mean $\sigma_{\bar{x}}$ of $n > I$ observations converges to 0 more slowly than the standard deviation σ_{MTE} of those observations in the sample, whose true errors are the least. This means that using only observations, which are real results from quantity measurements, we can obtain a value of the quantity that is near its true value than the sample mean $\sigma_{\bar{x}}$ is. Faster convergence to 0 has the standard deviation σ_{MTEA} but after a certain number of observations n , σ_{MTE} tends to σ_{MTEA} regardless of the data distribution. The findings in the current research correspond to the probability $Cv(n)$ of the existence in the sample of size n of more accurate observation than the sample mean [2] and explain the results in [1] produced by real data.

References

1. Cvetkov, V., (2024), "On initial data in adjustments of the geometric leveling networks (on the mean of paired observations)" *Journal of Geodetic Science*, vol. 14, no. 1, 2024, pp. 20220170,

<https://doi.org/10.1515/jogs-2022-0170> (accessed on 04.12.2024).

2. Cvetkov, V., (2024), AVERAGES, ENTROPY AND OBSERVATIONS. *Deutsche Internationale Zeitschrift Für Zeitgenössische Wissenschaft*, 93, 52–57, ISSN (Print) 2701-8369, ISSN (Online) 2701-8377, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14289165> (accessed on 07.12.2024).

3. Dekking F.M., Kraaikamp C., Lopuhaä H. P., L. E. Meester, (2005), *A Modern Introduction to Probability and Statistics: understanding why and how*, London, Springer – Verlag.

4. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Entropy> (accessed on 04.12.2024).

5. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Normal_distribution (accessed on 04.12.2024).

6. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_logarithmic_identities (accessed on 04.12.2024).